

Figure 1. Timeline of loss-of-function studies in *Medicago truncatula*. The graph is based on the first publication of each genetic locus, 673 loci in total. 219 of these genes were studied in the context of both symbiotic nitrogen fixation (SNF) and other processes. 380 loci were tested for SNF phenotypes and 512 for non-SNF phenotypes. On average, ca. 47 new genes have been characterized each year since 2020 (2025 excluded). The complete dataset consists of 565 published works and bioRxiv preprints as of 16 June 2025.